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Twitter Activism and Ethical Witnessing: Possibilities and Challenges of Feminist
Politics Against Gender-Based Violence

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Abstract

This article examines the proposals and challenges of digital activism on Twitter against gender-based violence with regards to the March 8 2017 feminist movement in Spain (8M). Exploramos una muestra de 20.000 mensajes (tweets, retwees y menciones) of the most commonly utilized hashtags in this context, such as #8M and #NiUnaMenos (Not one less [woman]), combinando instrumentos metodológicos cualitativos y cuantitativos para reflexionar sobre cómo es posible actuar desde un punto de vista político en la comunicación de los movimientos de protesta compartiendo experiencias sobre la violencia in highly mediated forms, como en el

caso del digital feminist activism en el marco del “platforms capitalism”. En el artículo nos ocupamos también de analizar if, in the case of 8M in Spain, digital feminist activism constituted a challenge to the hegemonic frames of representation of gender-based violence. The operationalization of the ethical testimony developed by Kelly Oliver pone de relieve la oportunidad que dar testimonio sobre la violencia de género ofrece al digital feminist activism para actuar de manera política y efectiva en Twitter circumventing la idea de que no es una red social conversacional y desafiando desventajas como la viralidad o la invisibilidad política.

Keywords

Feminist digital politics, Twitter, Spanish Hashtag feminism, gender-based violence, ethical witnessing

The following of the first worldwide feminist strike on March 8th, 2017 would not have been the same without the mobilizing capacity of thousands of digitally connected women. “We are united, we are international – and we are everywhere,” said Klementyna Suchanow, a Poland-based organiser of the International Women’s Strike (*The Guardian*, 2017). El “hashtag feminism”, una de las más populares formas de activismo feminista que utiliza las etiquetas para crear comunidades de conversación en Twitter (Mendes, Ringrose & Keller, 2018), funcionó a través de powerful hashtags still in use, such as #8M, #NiUnaMenos o #VivasNosQueremos, the latter two originating in Latin America and later garnering worldwide use. #ADayWithoutaWoman quickly became a popular hashtag on social media, calling on American women to participate in a national strike by taking the day off from

work, not shopping or wearing red in solidarity (*The New York Times*, 2017). These hashtags had the ability to organize, mobilize, revitalize, and unite positions in an unprecedented feminist political call to action. Digital feminist activism dissolved physical borders among women in over 50 countries who banded together to strike in response to the social, legal, political, moral, and verbal violence they experience around the globe (parodemujeres.com). The transformational capital of this multitude of connected women allowed for a widespread popular support and prepared the way for the 2018 strike, which became the object of international media interest. En este contexto de atención paid to digital activism, our study pretende ser una oportunidad para repensar la acción política feminista contra la violencia de género en Twitter desde una dimensión ética y política through an exploration of the most utilized hashtags around 8 March 2017 in Spain such as #8M and #NiUnaMenos. Following other projects in which we have studied the discursive production around sexist violence and the construction of the victim of gender violence (Fernández Romero, Núñez Puente, 2017; Núñez Puente, Fernández Romero, Rubira García, 2015; Gámez Fuentes, Núñez Puente, 2013), we wish to analyze whether or not Twitter discourses in the case of 8M entailed a challenge to hegemonic frames of representation of gender violence that contribute to the image of the vulnerability of the victim. To this end we will methodologically draw on the operationalization of Kelly Oliver's ethical testimony (2001, 2004) in order to understand whether such accounts involve a paradigm shift in the act of giving testimony of violence and if, therefore, this testimony that circulates through hashtags has a political character.

El “hashtag feminism” del 8 de marzo proceeded the viral #MeToo – #YoTambien in Spanish - through which thousands of women began to denounce experiences of sexual aggression and harassment on social media. La frase, iniciada por la activista africana Tarana Burke en 2006, obtuvo una impresionante atención cuando la actriz Alyssa Milano la usó como un hashtag de Twitter para denunciar the sexual assault by Hollywood producer Harvey Weinstein. The hashtag was tweeted nearly a million times in 48 hours, according to Twitter (CBS/AP, 2017).

Previamente, the #BeenRapedNeverReported hashtag, which trended in 2014, funcionó de forma similar al #MeToo in the ways in which it was used by girls and women to share personal stories of sexual violence and why they didn’t report them to authorities. En su estudio de ambos hashstg, Mendes, Ringrose & Keller discovered that “this solidarity often transforms into a feminist consciousness amongst hashtag participants, which allows them to understand sexual violence as a structural rather than personal problem” (pp. 237-238).

Una llamada para denunciar el acoso sexual bajo el hashtag #balancetonporc (“enseña a tu cerdo”) se hizo viral en la red social Twitter en Francia en octubre de 2017. El tweet que escribió la periodista francesa Sandra Muller invitaba a denunciar, ofreciendo nombres y apellidos, “un acoso sexual que hayas conocido en tu trabajo”. Más recientemente, en 2019, ha estallado el hashtag #MeTooEscritoresMexicanos que ha fomentado que centenares de mujeres del ámbito del la cultura den a conocer tanto sus propias experiencias de abuso, como los nombres y apellidos de las personas que las habían violentado. En menos de 24 horas y tras la explosión en Twitter, los presuntos abusadores ascendieron a 134 y las interacciones con la cuenta o con el hashtag superaban los 7 millones (Miguel, 2019).

Todos estos ejemplos de activismo digital feminista han atraído la atención de numerosas scholars que se han ocupado de indagar en la “growing trend of the public’s willingness to engage with resistance and challenges to sexism, patriarchy

and other forms of oppression via feminist uptake of digital communication". (Mendes, Ringrose and Keller, 2011: 236-237). Por su parte, la literatura científica sobre el activismo digital feminista ha explorado las posibilidades de transformación social vinculadas a las prácticas de resistencia problematizando los desafíos que para la acción política presentan dichas prácticas. Así Dean y Aune (2015: 391) señalan el modo en que plataformas como Facebook y Twitter hacen posible que las prácticas comunicativas de la llamada popular misogyny puedan ser contestadas de manera inmediata e, incluso, se ha argumentado cómo las redes sociales pueden contribuir a consolidar y crear una comunidad feminista (Evans & Chamberlain, 2015; Mendes, Ringrose, & Keller, 2018; Olson, 2016). Según Khoja-Moolji (2015: 349) a través de las acciones en el espacio digital se van creando comunidades de afecto que generan nuevas "intensidades afectivas" mediadas digitalmente por lo que ha sido llamado el "hashtag feminism" (Berridge & Portwood-Stacer, 2015; Horeck, 2014; Mendes, Ringrose, & Keller, 2018). Sin embargo, existe un debate creciente acerca de las oportunidades y amenazas que aportan las redes sociales como plataforma para el activismo feminista. Se ha advertido del potencial del llamado feminismo de Twitter no sin identificar, por otra parte, las debilidades que este presenta (Dean; Aune, 2015: 392). Therefore the digital activism of so many women has had to coexist in recent years with online misogyny (Banet-Weiser y Miltner, 2016), a product of the patriarchal structures, codes, and discourses that circulate on the web. Inserting the feminist voice in cyberspace and attempting to interrupt the flow of masculine codes is a radical act

(Wilding, 2004: 146) that obliges us to consider the challenges as well as the opportunities of digital feminist activism.

En este contexto, pretendemos analizar las formas de dar cuenta de la violencia de género centrándonos en la convocatoria del 8 de marzo en España a través de Twitter. En esa fecha, organizaciones de mujeres de todo el país llamaron a un "paro de empleo, cuidados y consumo" de media hora que comenzó a las 12:00 horas para sumarse a la huelga convocada a nivel mundial. Además de los paros a mediodía, se celebraron más de 50 actos entre manifestaciones, concentraciones y eventos culturales promovidos por las distintas coordinadoras feministas regionales. Miles de personas se sumaron a las movilizaciones convocadas en 49 ciudades españolas bajo el lema "Juntas y fuertes, feministas siempre" (Europa Press, 2017). Nuestra intención es comprender si a través del acto de dar testimonio se logró articular una respuesta política que remita a los fundamentos de la violencia de género. La aproximación que propone el testimonio ético supone, por una parte, asumir nuestra responsabilidad en cómo interpelamos y participamos en la producción del testimonio de la violencia y, por otra, comprender nuestra responsabilidad para con el o la Otra y para uno o una misma en aras de articular una respuesta que se sitúe en la dimensión política desde la recepción (Gámez, Gómez, Maseda, 2016).

March 8th, 2017: International Women's Strike for a Life without Violence

The first global strike of female productive and reproductive labor took place on March 8th, 2017. Women from more than 50 countries decided to strike in order to

demand a dignified life free from violence. The worldwide call to strike in 2017 was inspired by the mass mobilizations in Argentina two years prior to the shout of “*Ni una menos*” (Not one less [woman]), a slogan turned hashtag inspired by a poem by the murdered Mexican artist and activist Susana Chávez. The aim was to decry and put an end to the constant femicides in this countryⁱ.

In 2016, on October 3rd, “Black Monday” took place in Poland. Women self-convened a strike and were able to stop a draft bill that would have criminalized abortion, even in cases of rape or spontaneous abortions. The Women’s March in Washington, DC in January 2017 saw thousands of women from the United States and around the world take the streets after Donald Trump’s electoral victory to protest his sexist comments. Harnessing the distinct synergies amongst groups of women from different countries, by the end of 2016 the group International Women’s Strike was formed in order to promote a worldwide strike under the slogan “Solidarity is our weapon.” Their call made it clear that women were the indisputable protagonists of the strike, and offered first-person testimonies to the violence they had suffered while refusing to be considered as victimsⁱⁱ.

Aside from the physical gatherings, the website parodemujeres.com, with versions in Spanish and English, was fundamental to the articulation of the movement. . On Twitter, official accounts in English, <https://twitter.com/womensstrike>, Spanish <https://twitter.com/MujeresEnHuelga>, and in Polish <https://twitter.com/BlackMonday2016> were joined by other accounts from different countries. On February 22nd, 2017, women from the forty countries that had been supporting the coordination of the strike were called to join a global

Twitterstorm. The principal hashtag in Spanish, *#MujeresEnHuelga* (#Women on Strike) became a trending topic for more than six hours (Laudano, 2017). Other Spanish hashtags that achieved widespread circulation were *#8M*, *#NosotrasParamos*, (#WeStrike) *#VivasNosQueremos* and *#NiUnaMenos*. In particular, *#NiUnaMenos* became a global trending topic on June 3rd, 2015, Twitter in Spanish for being the first time this happened in relation to a topic associated with the feminist movement.

In Spain, organizations of women throughout the country called a strike on paid labor, caring work, and consumption in solidarity with the International Women's Strike bajo el lema "*#NosotrasParamos*" (López Álvarez, 2017). In workplaces, public institutions, and schools, participants organized a half-hour walkout, respaldados legalmente por el sindicato minoritario Confederación Intersindical, to protest against sexism, discrimination and violence against women (Zuil, 2017).. El movimiento feminista concitó a su vez a la huelga de cuidados y consumo para incluir a todas las mujeres que no trabajan fuera de casa pero que tienen cargas domésticas o compaginan ambos roles (Zuil, 2017). Durante toda la jornada se convocaron movilizaciones en 49 ciudades españolas logrando congregarse, solo en Madrid, a 500.000 personas, según la organización (Álvarez, Sauquillo, 2017) . The organizers rallied behind a blunt message: "*si nos matan, nos acosan, sufrimos discriminación, agresiones y brecha salarial, produzcan sin nosotras*" ("If they kill us, if they harass us, if we suffer discrimination, aggression, and wage disparities, then let them work without us") (Borraz, 2018). 8M was characterized as the "explosion" y de "momento histórico" (*madridiario.es*, 2017) of a movement

that had been actively growing online in a country in which between 2003 and 2016, 872 women were murdered by their partners or ex-partners (following official data from the *Ministerio de Presidencia, Relaciones con las Cortes e Igualdad* (Ministry of the President, Relations with the General Courts and Equality , 2018).

The most recent antecedent to the 8M protests was the November 7th, 2015 march against sexist violence that took the streets of Madrid to push for a bilateral agreement against violence towards women. The platform that drove the movement (<https://plataforma7n.wordpress.com/>) demanded that the concept of sexist violence include acts at the hands of others who are neither partners or ex-partners of the victims, given that the Integral Law of 2004 only addressed acts of violence in those contexts.. At that time there was talk of a resurgence of feminism with a larger presence of younger generations forming an active voice on social media. All these pressures led to the approval of the State Pact Against Gender Violence in September 2017 that proposed 213 concrete measures that the government would carry out within five years to fight against gender-based violence. In order to execute such measures, the government agreed to set aside €1B paid in annual installments of €200M beginning in 2018.

As such, the Bilateral Pact served to amplify a law that, although considered a legislative milestone, was problematic in that it did not consider the agency of the victims, conceptualizing them from a point of view looking towards state-sponsored welfare policy. Como algunas teóricas han señalado (Gámez Fuentes, Gómez Nicolau, & Maseda García, 2016; Gámez Fuentes, 2012), en la Comprehensive Law Against Gender-Based Violence se han enfatizado sobre todo los aspectos asistenciales,

sanitarios y jurídicos, contribuyendo así a situar al sujeto femenino en un espacio simbólico en el que este solo se constituye en la medida que denuncie y, por tanto, sea tutelado por el sistema. De este modo tanto la Comprehensive Law Against Gender-Based Violence como el Bilateral Pact ofrecen pocas herramientas para abordar y discutir críticamente el concepto de víctima y el de vulnerabilidad de manera que se visibilicen modos de superar la dicotomía víctima-sujeto agente.

All this paved the way for the declaration of a feminist strike on March 8th, 2018. In Spain, a work, student, care and consumption strike was carried out, lasting 24 hours with the support of several minority trade unions. On this occasion, the strategic utilization of alliances and dialogues, both in person and especially online, formed a cornerstone of the successful effort to garner widespread support for the strike. Las asambleas feministas de diferentes territorios crearon la Comisión 8M estatal como un espacio horizontal de trabajo, debate, organización, encuentro y apoyo mutuo. Dentro de ella, dos comisiones actedas liaisons between the media and online communication within the movement as well as its digital projection online and through social media.

The broad reception of the 8M tanto en 2017 como las sucesivas convocatorias de 2018 y 2019 call to strike showed the important moment in which the feminist movement in Spain found itself, substantially active and diverse both online and in the streets.

Ethical Testimony: Digital Feminist Politics and Narratives of Violence

Hegemonic frameworks of recognition, as we have seen in the instance of 8M in Spain, involve a visibilization of those processes through which dominant narratives are structured. Such narratives are susceptible, however, to challenges. From this starting point, this article investigates whether or not the discursive production on Twitter in relation to the 2017 8M movement in Spain made possible a challenge to the hegemonic frames of representation of gender-based violence, and if so how testimony to it is given (Fernández Romero & Núñez Puente, 2017; Fernández Romero, 2019). To this end the project utilizes, on one hand, Kelly Oliver's (2001) concept of ethical testimony, and on the other, an analytical consideration of the aspect of the logic of visibility and circulation in the digital economy. La circularidad y la visibilidad como categorías preeminentes que definen las prácticas digitales han sido críticamente discutidas en relación al potencial político del feminista digital activism (Smith-Prei & Stehle, 2016; Tanenbaun, 2015). Se ha abordado el modo en que el activism works in the digital age haciendo posible el rewriting de la digital economy precisamente explorando cómo la circulación de los mensajes en el entorno digital puede activar una respuesta política al contrario de lo que se ha sostenido desde otras posiciones teóricas (Dean, 2005). Se trataría, en este caso, de un activismo digital que, si bien no puede detach from the economy that enables it, posibilita la emergencia de espacios de resistencia y de creación de comunidad más allá de los consumption patterns que articulan la neoliberal digital economy (Smith-Prei & Stehle, 2016: 11) Por otra parte, el carácter políticamente transformador, o no, de la visibilidad ha sido addressed para discutirlo en relación a las prácticas del activismo feminista en las redes sociales. Feminist media scholars como Banet-

Weiser (2018) advierten del cambio/shift que ha permitido pasar en el entorno digital de la politics of visibility a la economy of visibility. Así mientras la politics of visibility recoge las demandas de los sujetos marginalized para ser reconocidos (their demand to be seen) y propiciar así un cambio social, la economy of visibility en el current media environment hace que la visibility becomes an end in itself.

Teniendo en cuenta las posibilidades de la incorporación crítica de la circularidad y la visibilidad en las prácticas digitales feministas, la exploración del testimonio ético en las redes sociales se podría considerar, a nuestro juicio, como un modo de intervenir desde el activismo digital desafiando las lógicas de la economía digital neoliberal mediante la creación de oportunidades de resistencia.

Por otra parte, habitualmente, la discusión en torno al potencial político de las tecnologías para reconfigurar la participación política (Mossberger et al., 2007 y Gil de Zúñiga et al., 2010) y de la capacidad de Internet para generar cambio social se ha planteado en términos dicotómicos y muy maximalistas (Chadwick y Howard, 2010; Chadwick, 2017). En este caso, nos interesa señalar que actualmente los medios sociales (Boyd, 2010) monopolizan la opinión pública a través de un modelo que forma una nueva “cultura participativa” (Jenkins, 2008). Esta mayor facilidad en la comunicación en tiempo real, potencialmente global, sencilla y anónima ha posibilitado mayores espacios de deliberación (Fuchs, 2013). En el caso concreto del activismo se ha terminado produciendo un objeto de investigación bastante extenso, poliédrico y multicapa (Flesher y Gillan, 2017) que corre el peligro de convertirse en un “fuzzy term” (Kaun y Uldam, 2018). En efecto, Morozov (2011, 2013) ha mostrado cómo esta cultura participativa es co-optada por los agentes hegemónicos de poder al convertirse en un fin en sí mismo (Banet-Weiser, 2018). Se trata por tanto de tener en cuenta que esta cultura participativa, que se apoya en la politics of visibility, no escapa a una economy of visibility que acaba conformando el espacio hegemónico mainstream.

No obstante, a pesar de estas limitaciones y críticas, Twitter sigue siendo el medio social a través del cual se han expresado y articulado demandas sociales en ámbitos tan diferentes como protestas activistas en Brasil (Recuero, Zago, Bastos, & Araújo, 2015), las Gezi protest en Turquía (Oz, 2016; Vatikiotis & Yörük, 2016), el 15M en España (Peña-López, Congosto, & Aragón, 2014) o el cambio de imagen de la ciudad de Flint, USA (Moors, 2019). Todos estos ejemplos de cómo, a través del uso de este medio social, el activismo ha conseguido modificar espacio de comunicación mainstream. En el caso de nuestro análisis, el testimonio ético nos servirá para discutir si los hashtag analizados son efectivos a la hora de building networks of solidarity y produce communities of conversation (Medes, Ringrose & Keller, 2018). Para ello debemos tener presente que los ethical testimonies articulate themselves through the possibilities forwarded by representational and spectatorial action as a political response. That is to say, giving an ethical testimony supposes not only recognizing what is represented in the account, but also going beyond that to stimulate political action upon reception through the act of recognition of both the testimony itself as well as those who give and receive the testimony.

This phenomenon is of special interest for critically approaching narratives about gender-based violence in Spain and how these have, or have not, been transformed following the political and social initiatives that have unfolded in a relevant manner in the media accounts with high impact on digital discourses (Núñez Puente, 2011). Following the approval of the Organic Law 1/2004 of December 28th, titled Comprehensive Measures of Protection Against Gender-Based Violence, Spain saw increased attention towards gender-based violence in the media and social debate. The approval of this law in 2004 represented a turn towards state welfare policy articulated through a judicial response. Such policies, however, left

aside the consideration of the victims as politically capable subjects, and ignored their presence in accounts which had become a refutation of the hegemonic narratives of gender-based violence. This failure to recognize the victim as an agentic subject began a process of hypervisualization, which lead to fetishization, representationally turning the victim into an object of media consumption (Núñez Puente and Gámez Fuentes, 2012). In this manner, and on the contrary, we assert that exploring the transformative possibilities of representation of the victim as a subject capable of converting the account of violence into a political act is fundamental for uncovering the structural conditions from which this violence emerges as well. The critical examination of the testimony in the accounts of violence is founded, then, on the ethical-political axis of the recognition of the other, of her subjectivity, and of her agency (Butler, 2005). This is a recognition that coincides in the diverse intersecting axes of violence with other inequalities and which situates subjects in social positions beyond that of the individual (Fraser, 2012). These intersections work towards the activation of our responsibility as receptors and constructors of narratives about gender violence, while they reinforce the necessity of accountability. This accountability categorically situates itself in a relational capacity between the subject who suffers violence and the structures that sustain it. This relational paradigm allows for both the causes as well as the reparation of gender-based violence to emerge (Butler, 2005).

Our analytical model, as we have noted, is based on a model of operationalization of the theoretical concept of the ethical testimony (Gómez, Gómez, Maseda, 2016) that unfolds in four analytic dimensions:

1. The relation between the testifier and the witness. In this first aspect of analysis, we consider the relational logics between the testifier, that is, she who gives the testimony, and the witness, who receives said testimony. This representational logic is essential in order to delve into innovative communication initiatives tied to political action. Moving past representation in favor of a dynamic that puts us in relation with the other beyond representation in the hegemonic framework is the starting point for an ethical recognition of the other.
2. Content of the testimony of gender-based violence can be constructed in a general manner without a specific articulation that takes into account how violence is generated discursively and how this construction responds to dominant patterns of representation. The search for new productions of meaning that elide hegemonic shared accounts would make it possible to reveal conditions in which the violence emerges that were previously rendered unintelligible.
3. Construction of resistance from a point of vulnerability. Injurability defines the intrinsic and permanent condition of being wounded on which women are representationally constructed (Butler and Athanasiou, 2013). The lack of agency, understood as the capacity to articulate one's subjectivity, leads to the invariable representation of women as needing to be rescued by

others. This other may be an individual other or a social other, such as the State policies deriving from juridical and welfare discourses as they relate to gender-based violence. In the dominant accounts, the victim of gender-based violence is only understood through her victimhood, stripped of any political engagement. Precisely, a detailed examination of accounts of gender-based violence drawing on ethical testimony offers us insights into those other communication initiatives in which resistances are sought in spaces of vulnerability.

4. Links with the general framework of struggles and demands in which narratives about gender-based violence are inscribed. The ethical positioning of accounts of gender-based violence involves accounting for those testimonies and accounts that favor the revelation of those structural conditions that make violence possible. Therefore, from an ethical testimony approach, the analysis of accounts of violence must pause to examine the link between these narratives and the strategies of collective resistance that make violence visible, which is tightly linked to the structural inequalities that allow for it.

The analytical model of the ethical testimony enables us to study digital practices in relation to 8M in Spain, while, at the same time, as we have noted, exploring new accounts of violence and of the victim in the context of feminist digital politics. We cannot critically address the digital practices of feminist activism in the context of 8M without bearing in mind the communicative space in which

they were produced. The logics of the digital economy have potentially increased the political capacity for activism while it has problematized the reach and definition of feminist politics (Smith-Prei and Maria Stehle, 2016). ~~The materiality and the immediacy of digital practices involve a fixation on notions such as visibility that are tied to other such as accumulation and circularity. Digital practices allow us to broadcast our own narratives or channel our political actions, but they also allow the circulation of messages without a message, information incapable of generating debate (Dean, 2005), which are capable of depoliticizing digital feminist politics.~~ In this regard, we must consider that the neoliberal aspect of the subject does not only stem from an economic rationality (Gill, 2018) but also efficiently hinges on concepts such as accumulation, linked to visibility, and in opposition to political action. ~~It is worth questioning, therefore, if political transformation of certain accounts of gender based violence enabled by the neoliberal digital economy is, paradoxically, possible.~~ Through the analytic tool of ethical testimony, *tratamos de buscar modos de hacer inteligible la narración, con carácter ético y político, de la violencia de género en contextos mediados.. . Todo ello teniendo en cuenta que los actos políticos de activismo digital se ven condicionados por lo que se ha denominado “platform capitalism” en el que prevalece el continuado traffic and circulation of the content (Srniczek, 2016). As such, our analysis centers on resolving some of the questions that arise when we critically approach the manner in which testimony is given or digital narratives of gender based violence are constructed.* We ask if it is possible to break from the hegemonic framework that produces circulation of content driven by the logics of the neoliberal digital economy (Steihn).

~~This allows us to also question if a disruptive transformation of the hegemonic frames in which violence is made comprehensible, passing from the neoliberal dimension of the communicative subject to the other subject understood in a relational process of searching for the other, is possible.~~

Finally, the concept of ethical testimony, and its operationalization, can offer us an empirical and theoretical framework from which we might reveal further issues in regards to the political implications of digital feminist practices that can be used both in academic research and for feminists activist to improve their communication network strategies. El concepto del testimonio ético nos permite así abordar y problematizar cuestiones tales como la dimensión relacional de la comunicación. El paradigma del testimonio ético, por tanto, haría posible repensar críticamente un proceso relacional de la comunicación en el que al hecho de dar un testimonio de la violencia de género, compartido en mediated forms and predicated on la acción colectiva, se le ascriba un carácter político y en el que to make one visible no dependa, sobre todo, on numerical accumulation (Banet-Weiser, en prensa).

Methodology

In order to empirically observe and adequately evaluate whether or not an ethical testimony on the 8M strike has been given via Twitter, we have initially proceeded to operationalize it through dimensions and indicators that allow for the mediation and visualization in the digital context.

The first proposed dimension of the ethical testimony relative to the *testifier-witness* relationship refers to the production of the message and the identification of

the actors who participate in the conversation on social media. The most direct way in which to approach the ethical testimony is by analyzing the most influential, active, and popular accounts involved in the conversation with the highest volume of posts and number of followers. Given that the number of users who participate in a Twitter conversation may be quite high, the criteria for influence based on mediation activity and popularity are very common, especially PageRank/weight-out-degree and number of followers. These network measurements indicate the most central users (with the most connections) and with the most followers who participate in the spreading of messages (Baeza-Yates, R. (2004); Brin, S., Page, L. (1998)).

The second dimension points to the *content of the ethical testimony*, to the specific information and the subjects discussed, particularly in relation to those matters related to gender-based violence and to the victims, which are the central focus of this article. In order to conveniently study this aspect in a Twitter hashtag, we undertake an analysis of the content of tweets sent in the context of the March 8, 2017 strikes in Spain. Through an analysis of the lexical frequencies of these tweets, namely the repetition of certain terms and words, we can rank the content, observing the relative importance (saliency) of each theme. Similarly, we may compile the most common and frequent pairs of words as a measure of the most repeated or represented topics in the discourse.

The third aspect, dedicated to the *construction of vulnerability and resistance*, may be identified through an analysis of the produced conversations. Specifically, we look to register the level of responses, discussions, and deliberations that are

produced on Twitter. These interactions are an indicator of the creation of cohesive conversational communities. There are a series of general measurements such as the number of retweets, commonly associated with the “stickiness” of a message and its dissemination without modification, while mentions and responses are more associated with the creation of stronger interactions within communicational spaces and tend to generate conversational communities which modify messages.

Finally, the fourth aspect has to do with the act of *connecting the demands of the movement to other more general or global frameworks*. This involves verifying the appearance in the conversation of other matters, movements, protests, expressions, social or political themes, etc., linked somehow to these interactions related to gender-based violence. This may be measured in at least two ways: by a reading of the content (in search of terms and lexicons related to other social movements and political demands), as well as by identifying the appearance of other political actors in the conversation.

Table 1 synthesizes this operationalization:

[Insert Table 1 about here]

From this operationalization, the next step is obtaining data. Using the NodeXL software (<https://www.smrfoundation.org/nodexl/>)ⁱⁱⁱ, we selected the two most representative hashtags, #8M and #NiUnaMenos, used between March 7 and March 8th, 2017, obtaining a corpus of approximately 20,500 tweets. We consider this to be a sufficiently large sample (assuming that the Twitter API allows for random and not necessarily comprehensive access to tweets) and that having obtained it during the

specific dates of the mobilization (Morstatter, Pfeffer, & Liu, 2014). Dentro de este espacio, buscamos identificar los contenidos afines con el modelo teórico. Si entendemos los hashtags como aglutinadores de información en torno a las cuentas más populares, serán este tipo de cuentas las que difundan el contenido que se convertirá en hegemónico. The tweets represent the principal types of conversation.

Es conocido que este tipo de investigación plantea problemas de representatividad (Blank, 2017a, 2017b), así como un cierto sesgo geográfico y orientado a las cuentas más activas (Bruns & Liang, 2012). Estos sesgos no afectan esta investigación porque precisamente se busca encontrar las tendencias hegemónicas (más frecuentes); no rastrear todo el conjunto de tweets ni generalizar o extrapolar estos resultados automáticamente. Si bien el hashtag puede tener múltiples significados, dentro de las cuentas más activas funciona como un aglutinador semántico de significados (Recuero, Zago, Bastos, & Araújo, 2015). Es decir, nuestro análisis persigue ver si se reproducen algunos de los supuestos teóricos del esquema planteado en torno a los hashtags analizados, y no tanto comprobar si todas las cuentas lo cumplen. Así, el sesgo hacia las cuentas más activas precisamente nos facilita ver este fenómeno a través de diversas métricas de Twitter reconocidas y aceptadas científicamente (Bruns & Stieglitz, 2013).

Para el análisis exploratorio de aquellas dimensiones que requieren una clasificación de los tweets no se ha utilizado una codificación concreta porque lo que se ha planteado es un análisis de contenido básico de frecuencias léxicas dada la naturaleza discursiva de los datos, simples mensajes cortos de pocos caracteres. Es decir, se ha hecho un recuento de las palabras más utilizadas en los mensajes como primera aproximación al contenido de los tweets. Posteriormente, sí se ha accedido manualmente a los perfiles de cada una de las cuentas para categorizarlas. Los análisis realizados simplemente establecen tendencias respecto al contenido explícito de los tweets, tipos de cuentas más activas, formatos de redes sociales que se generan en esos hashtags. Es decir, basic content analytics (CA) integrating text mining and network analytics que nos permita mostrar el uso o ausencia de ciertos términos (violencia, víctima, etc.) en la medida que su aparición, o ausencia, muestra

en qué medida los reclamos del movimiento activista permean en las cuentas más populares y son utilizados por los medios masivos de comunicación (Moors, 2019). . The data selected for later analysis are recorded in an Excel spreadsheet that indicates the broadcast nodes (tweeters, or users who write tweets) and a whole series of network measurements (about these users, their activity, the receptors, the content of tweets, etc.) For the posterior analysis, we used the same Excel spreadsheet with the Atlas.ti qualitative analysis program and the Gephi software for social media analysis and visualization.

Analysis

Applying the operationalized dimensions objects of the above table, with respect to the #8M hashtag we can observe:

In the **first** analytic dimension we found that the top 25 most active accounts participating in the conversation correspond to parties or individuals directly related to institutional politics (8), activists and/or influencers not necessarily related to the movement (7), famous individuals (7), and the media (3). Table 2 shows the top 25 accounts in regards to total interaction (Tweets + Mentions + Replies To) together with a typological characterization according to the type of account.

[Insert Table 2 about here]

The data shows us that, while the accounts specifically associated with the movement have a presence, they do not extensively cover the conversation and share the space with other actors. . Por ejemplo, el tweet vinculado al hashtag 8M del coordinador general del movimiento político Izquierda Unida Alberto Garzón,

“Este #8M nos unimos al Paro Internacional de Mujeres. Apoyando a las #MujeresDelMundo en su lucha por la emancipaci... <https://t.co/PVU1Q6f7ol>” (@garzon), propició una importante interacción. Mayor movimiento aún generó el tweet de este político vinculado al hashtag NiUnaMenos, desde una perspectiva simpatizante con la convocatoria: “Feliz día de la mujer. Cada día, sin embargo, es un día de lucha contra el patriarcado. #NiUnaMenos <https://t.co/RIOov8Fcp4>”. Sin embargo, la cuenta de comunicación feminista argentina @_manifiesta_ obtuvo menos repercusión a través de un tweet que autoconvocaba a la huelga e interpelaba a las mujeres para secundar el paro: “El #8M nosotras (nos) paramos. #ParoInternacionalDeMujeres #8M #NosotrasParamos #VivasNosQueremos:... <https://t.co/D6YfsFkYD6>”.

The trend is that, although the movement is visible, it does not escape the inertia of the communicational dynamic in which retweets of accounts outside the movement dominate. The large disproportion between the mentions and the replies shows that the relation between who sends the message and who spreads it does not cease to be, for a significant number of accounts, a connection of relatively minor adhesion. This is an expected normal characteristic due to the type of media analyzed and because of the inertia that social desirability generates within the social context.

In the **second** analytic dimension, relative to the content, Table 3 shows words with a frequency of repetition greater than 1,000 instances. However, we include two terms (“strike” and “patriarchy”) just below this threshold due to their semiotic importance to the object of study. It is worth noting that the most repeated words and themes are general expressions in relation to #8M and the corresponding strike. Immediately following, we found words related to the global dimension the movement gained and the associated (unpaid) care work strikes (nosotrasparamos, internacional, Lucha).

[Insert Table 3 about here]

However, we see that certain themes issues are not as visible or frequent: With the exception of the word “patriarchy,” in general we see very general or abstract mentions of violence, such as certain adjectives (*machista*: N=285; *violencia+violencias* (violence+violences): N=941), common activist slogans or phrases (stop: N=29; *contralabrechasalarial* (against the wage gap): N=13; *mujerescontraelracismo* (women against racism): N=5) and other minor mentions. In this sense, the content framework reflects a rather general discursive scheme in support of or related to the feminist strike. Tables 4 and 5 corroborate this analysis.

[Insert Table 4 about here]

[Insert Table 5 about here]

Both the most-frequent word pairs and the most-used hashtags show the relationship between the 8M movement and #niunamenos, as well as a orientation towards the caregiving strike and the successful protest that took place that day (El País, 2017; Sahuquillo & Álvarez, 2017). It is important for our discussion to note the relatively few mentions of the term “*víctima*” (“victim”) (N=18). The feminist movement insists in avoiding those terms that stigmatize women and transform them in marked persons (Casado Neira & Martínez, 2016). Su escaso uso se realizó en diferentes sentidos. Por un lado, como adefinitorio de quien da testimonio de la

violencia e interpela al testigo tratando de generar accountability, esto es, rendición de cuentas: “#8M #NosotrasParamos para q la policía y lxs magistradx nos crean cuando denunciemos ser víctimas d violencia o que lo son nuestrxs hijxs” (@perlaprig). Por otro lado, reproducía el uso común y acrítico de la palabra por parte de los medios o de partidos políticos para referirse a quienes sufren violencia: “La actriz Brie Larson, defensora de víctimas de la violencia machista <https://t.co/LupkcfABzb>: ‘El cine es una forma de activismo’. #8M” (@docemiradas); “#Canarias es la segunda comunidad en número de mujeres víctimas de violencia de machista de todo el estado... <https://t.co/oaWPyXDNG2>” (@podemoscanarias). Asimismo, el concepto se incluyó dentro de un hashtag que precisamente negaba la condición de víctimas a las mujeres. El tweet que publicó un fotoperiodista con esta etiqueta no generó, no obstante, ninguna interacción: “#8M Constituimos + d la mitad d la población dl mundo y sabemos q el poder está en nuestras manos #NoSomosVictimas... <https://t.co/MbtZqNMaRx>” (@juansantiso). The low frequency with which this term appears is evidence of the success of such insistence within the conversational community, even among the most popular users, especially when compared with the frequent use of the term “*violencia*” (“violence”) (N=941). Hemos de tener en cuenta, sin embargo, que la victimización de las mujeres no se produce solo a partir del uso de este concepto. Es el caso del siguiente tweet, que sin hacer uso de la palabra, incidió en la vulnerabilidad y en la no agencia de las mujeres, además de realizar un controvertido juego de palabras con respecto al no maltrato cotidiano: “Hoy es el Día Internacional de la Mujer. No te olvides de respetarlas, cuidarlas y no maltratarlas todos los días” (@Dosbrosuy). Es interesante también señalar cómo algunos tweets, con bastantes retweets y favs, lograron colocar la atención sobre la posibilidad de apoyar y favorecer la huelga, dando pistas sobre ello a los hombres simpatizantes: “¿SOS HOMBRE Y QUERÉS SUMARTE AL PARO/MARCHA DE MUJERES DEL #8M? 1. Si sos padre encárgate de tus hijxs. 2. Si sos amigo ofrécete de niño”. (@_suniac).

In the **third** analytic dimension, we find a series of rather fragmented and disperse communities with few responses or mentions. Moreover, as Table 6 shows, responses to tweets do not surpass 1% of total messages, which indicates a diffusion with a great deal of following and consensus, but hardly any discussion or exchange.

[Insert Table 6 about here]

In other words, we do not find ourselves faced with strong conversational communities, but rather a massive diffusion of messages with hardly any discussion or deliberation. However, when we analyze these communities in relation to the degree of mutual relations or the quantity of connections established, we may begin to note some differences. The measures of popularity and/or authority are not useful because, as we have developed in the first analytic dimension, the greatest activity is dominated by instrumental messages from famous individuals or organizations. As such, the appropriate metric with which to measure these relations is the betweenness centrality (Ediger et al., 2010; Gruzd, Wellman, & Takhteyev, 2011; Rajasingh, Rajan, & D, 2009; Tremayne, 2014). It is defined by the number of paths between any two nodes passing through a given node, as opposed to the number of possible paths between those two nodes. We could say that it is a measure of the power held by a given node as a result of the 'monopoly' of the roads that lead to one or more specific groups (Grabowicz et al., 2012; Park & Suh, 2013). Therefore, this measure gives us an alternative to PageRank/Out degree previously

seen. Table 7 shows a summary of the 30 accounts with the highest level of betweenness, maintaining the same characterization from Table 2. For clarity, this time we have eliminated those accounts that were impossible to characterize.

[Insert Table 7 about here]

Note that institutional accounts and accounts of famous people have a much lower presence in this table. And, despite the lack of solid conversational communities, when they are produced, they are typically a product of female activist users and related to the principal demands analyzed in this article: gender-based violence and the feminist strike.

Finally, in regards to the **fourth** dimension pertaining to connections with other frames, certain links to issues about employment labor, trade unions or care work stand out. Through the analysis and the tables presented previously, we may reflect on the fact that within the most active accounts (dimension 1), we do not find any clear trend related to struggles outside the feminist movement salvo algunas excepciones, como la de la periodista e influencer Cristina Fallarás, quien enlazó a un vídeo que conectaba el paro feminista con otras luchas para transformar el sistema político, económico y social que favorece las violencias machistas: “¿Os he contado ya que el #8M no trabajaré? El vídeo lo cuenta. ¿Tú qué harás? #NosotrasParamos #NiUnaMenos... <https://t.co/k8ZuQUKnZ1>” (@LaFallaras).. El tweet del político Gabriel Rufián en el que ampliaba la mirada al machismo y la opresión obtuvo una alta interacción: 'Machismo es el miedo de los hombres a las mujeres sin miedo.' Galeano 'Toda opresión crea un estado de guerra.' De Beauvoir #NiUnaMenos (@Gabrielrufian). We also do not see strong links within the lexicographic analysis (dimension 2), in which terms related to the mobilization and the associated strike predominate. Cuando se hace referencia a las “víctimas”, generalmente se infiere o se explicita que se está aludiendo a las mujeres que sufren violencia: “21 víctimas en

apenas dos meses. ¡Basta ya! #NiUnaMenos #VivasNosQueremos #NiUnaMas #EnVolemVives <https://t.co/G0aCFiEaEK>" (@javieroboe). Instead, in our sample we may see that the structure of the community that converses (dimension 3), though not quantitatively notable, does so in a dialogue in which union organizations and activists participate. Demands related to labor and other matters appear, to an extent, as linked inasmuch as union organizations echo the strike. But these are somewhat smaller overshadowed and their links to other struggles can be difficult to observe with clarity. In this sense, while we cannot affirm that a strong connection with other frameworks has been identified, there are indeed gestures towards relations with the sphere of employment, domestic labor, human trafficking, trade unions and immigration.

[Insert Table 8 about here]

Conclusions

The study of the possible mobilizing capacity of the hashtags #8M and #NiUnaMenos (Not one [woman] fewer) which circulated on Twitter on March 7th and 8th, 2017 and the challenge they pose to the hegemonic frames of representation of gender-based violence shows that in Spain the circulation of messages may result in a certain depoliticizing practice while at the same time being capable of giving ethical testimony.

The analysis of the production of the message and the identification of the actors who participated in the Twitter conversation within the context of the studied hashtags show the general trend in this media, that this conversation was coopted, in large part, by accounts not specifically associated with the feminist movement, but rather related to institutional politics, activists and/or influencers

(not always tied to the movement) famous people, and the media. As a result the testimony about violence did not circulate widely, as was expected in relation to the accounts of the movement itself, and therefore there was no recognition of who gives and receives such testimonies.

However, we see in an analysis of the content that these actors did appropriate some of the themes that did circulate through the official accounts here considered, linking the strike to care work or the patriarchy. This link is, however, not always present, given that there are very general or abstract mentions of violence, a concept that is highly present in the communications that called the worldwide strike. As we have seen, the term 'victim' is hardly utilized, which we may interpret as an accomplishment of the feminist movement in that the global call associated the strike with sisterhood, solidarity, and with women as agents capable of exercising resistance from their position of vulnerability. This can give us the general idea that besides being coopted, the activist movement was able to put some demands in the general mainstream conversation.

Within the logics of visibility and circulation on Twitter, there appears to be in this case a generalized mass diffusion of messages with little discussion or debate. This practice, identified by Dean (2005) as the spreading of messages without a message, is nevertheless revealed to be distinct upon analyzing the level of mutual relations or quantity of links established between users. In this regard, we note that the female activist users are the only ones capable of establishing small, solid communities in relation to the fight against gender-based violence and to the feminist strike. These small communities are precisely those capable of

linking the demands of feminist activism with other struggles. Still, this is a connection that is established only lightly with domestic domestic labor, human trafficking, the workplace, or immigration to the feminist movement.

Ultimately, in the results from the first two dimensions of the analysis we see that the majority of tweets, as well as the most frequently used words, replicate the mottos of the activist movement and are sent by accounts instrumental to the movement. However, in this respect, we consider it important to keep in mind at least two factors. First, that within the Spanish political context in 2017, with a conservative government against the protest and strike, the mere mass diffusion of the hashtags may be considered, to a certain extent, as a challenge to the hegemonic framework. Second, the very characteristics of social media favor these types of messages at the expense of other forms of media more favorable to the debate and the fact that some demands from the activist movement were present is remarkable.

At the same time, the results obtained in the third and fourth analytic dimensions highlight the fact that the existence of debate and contact with other struggles takes form in marginal communities ((Weimann, 1982) outside of the general conversation. For this reason, even if we may intuit some lines that, with nuances, indicate the presence of depoliticizing messages, we must keep in mind that the media analyzed is prone to and favors this sort of communication.

The analysis of the activist proposals of Spanish digital feminism against gender-based violence has allowed us to address certain trends in relation to the possibilities and challenges that we must critically deal with feminist politics in order to discuss the way in which digital activism could become a more effective tool for intervention. El testimonio ético abre así nuevas posibilidades para el

activismo digital feminista de manera que este, mediante el énfasis en la dimensión compartida de dar testimonio de la violencia de género, pueda conseguir challenge tanto la flattening de los messages como la despolitización resultante de las demandas de carácter meramente individual. Dar testimonio se podría convertir así en un instrumento comunicativo que propiciaría oportunidades de resistencia asentadas en un sentido de la solidaridad y la comunidad en las que the act of coming forward in highly mediated forms como Twitter resultaría en un verdadero acto de transformación social. La operacionalización del testimonio ético en el caso del 8M en España muestra que Twitter es capaz de difundir mensajes masivos que los movimientos sociales pueden instrumentalizar políticamente ofreciendo testimonio colectivo sobre la violencia. Esto contribuye a potenciar la accountability, esto es, la posibilidad de petición de rendición de cuentas por parte de quien ofrece el testimonio a quien lo recibe. Frente al uso actual de las redes que favorecen la comunicación de forma privada como Instagram o WhatsApp, plataformas como Twitter podrían impulsar la vuelta al uso de la agencia activa más propio del origen de las redes sociales. El testimonio ético permite, por tanto, visibilizar el potencial de las redes sociales (Moore, 2019: 809). El testimonio ético permite, por tanto, visibilizar el potencial de los social media para el activismo digital al hacer posible complicate and intervene in the dominant narratives.

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References

- Agudo, A. (2018, March, 7). Feminismos en el sur global: más allá del #MeToo. *Elpais.com*. Retrieved from https://elpais.com/elpais/2018/03/05/planeta_futuro/1520264833_411476.html
- Álvarez, P., Sahuquillo, M. R. (2017, March 9). Miles de mujeres marchan en España por la igualdad de derechos. *Elpais.com*. Retrieved from https://elpais.com/politica/2017/03/08/actualidad/1488980420_408460.html
- Baeza-Yates, R. (2004). Excavando la web. *El profesional de la información*, 13(1), 4-10.
- Banet-Weiser, S. (2015). Keynote Address: Media, Markets, Gender: Economies of Visibility in a Neoliberal Moment. *The Communication Review*, 18(1), 53–70. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714421.2015.996398>

Banet-Weiser, S. (2018) *Empowered: popular feminism and popular misogyny*. Duke University Press, Durham.

Berridge S and Portwood-Stacer L (2015) Introduction: Feminism, hashtags and violence against women and girls. *Feminist Media Studies*, 15(2): 341–344.

Blank, G. (2017a). The Digital Divide Among Twitter Users and Its Implications for Social Research. *Social Science Computer Review*, 35(6), 679-697. <https://doi.org/10/gckjnp>

Blank, G. (2017b, abril 10). Did you consider Twitter's (lack of) representativeness before doing that predictive study? — Oxford Internet Institute [Blog]. Recuperado 9 de abril de 2019, de Oxford Internet Institute website: <https://www.oii.ox.ac.uk/blog/did-you-consider-twitters-lack-of-representativeness-before-doing-that-predictive-study/>

Borraz, M. (2017, March 18). Las mujeres toman la calle por la igualdad de derechos en una marcha de asistencia récord. *Eldiario.es*. Retrieved from https://www.eldiario.es/sociedad/mujeres-calle-laboral-reivindicar-derechos_0_620138657.html

Boyd, D. (2010). Social Network Sites as Networked Publics: Affordances, Dynamics and Implications. In Z. Papacharissi (Ed.), *Networked Self: Identity, Community, and Culture on Social Network sites* (pp. 39-58). London: Routledge.

Brin, S., Page, L. (1998). "The Anatomy of a Large-Scale Hypertextual Web Search Engine". Seventh International World-Wide Web Conference (WWW 1998), Abril 14-18, Brisbane, Australia.

Bruns, A., & Liang, Y. E. (2012). Tools and methods for capturing Twitter data during natural disasters. *First Monday*, 17(4). <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v17i4.3937>

Bruns, A., & Stieglitz, S. (2013). Towards more systematic Twitter analysis : metrics for tweeting activities. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 16, 91-108. <https://doi.org/10/gfx5zx>

- Butler, J. (2005). *Giving an Account of Oneself: A Critique of Ethical Violence*. New York: Fordham University Press.
- Butler, J., & Athanasiou, A. (2013). *Dispossession. The Performative in the Political*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Butler, J., Gambetti, Z., & Sabsay, L. (Eds.) (2016). *Vulnerability in Resistance*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Cadwalladr, C. (2018, March 18). 'I made Steve Bannon's psychological warfare tool': meet the data war whistleblower. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/news/2018/mar/17/data-war-whistleblower-christopher-wylie-faceook-nix-bannon-trump>
- Cadwalladr, C., & Graham-Harrison, E. (2018, March 17). Revealed: 50 million Facebook profiles harvested for Cambridge Analytica in major data breach. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/news/2018/mar/17/cambridge-analytica-facebook-influence-us-election>
- Casado Neira, D., & Martínez, M. (2016). La víctima simulada. Identidades forzadas en la violencia de género. *Política y Sociedad*, 53(3), 879-896. https://doi.org/10.5209/rev_POSO.2016.v53.n3.49719
- CBS/AP (2017) More than 12M 'MeToo' Facebook posts, comments, reactions in 24 hours. *Cbsnews.com*. Retrieved from: <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/metoo-more-than-12-million-facebook-posts-comments-reactions-24-hours/>

Chadwick, A., & Howard, P. N. (Eds.) (2010). *Routledge handbook of Internet politics*.

Taylor & Francis.

Chadwick, A. (2017). *The hybrid media system: Politics and power*. Oxford University

Press.

Dean, J. (2005). Communicative Capitalism: Circulation and the Foreclosure of

Politics. *Cultural Politics*, 1(1), 51-74. DOI: 10.2752/174321905778054845

Dean, J.; Aune, K. (2015). Feminism Resurgent? Mapping Contemporary Feminist

Activisms in Europe. *Social Movement Studies*, v. 14, 375-395.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/14742837.2015.1077112>

Ediger, D., Jiang, K., Riedy, J., Bader, D. A., Corley, C., Farber, R., & Reynolds, W. N.

(2010). Massive Social Network Analysis: Mining Twitter for Social Good. In

2010 39th International Conference on Parallel Processing (pp. 583–593).

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPP.2010.66>

EFE (2017, March 3). Movilizaciones en 50 ciudades lanzan un "grito común" por la

igualdad y contra la violencia machista. www.rtve.es. Retrieved from:

[http://www.rtve.es/noticias/20170308/movilizaciones-50-ciudades-](http://www.rtve.es/noticias/20170308/movilizaciones-50-ciudades-lanzan-grito-comun-igualdad-contra-violencia-machista/1500760.shtml)

[lanzan-grito-comun-igualdad-contra-violencia-machista/1500760.shtml](http://www.rtve.es/noticias/20170308/movilizaciones-50-ciudades-lanzan-grito-comun-igualdad-contra-violencia-machista/1500760.shtml)

EFE (2018, March 8). Una marea morada de mujeres clama en Valencia contra la

discriminación. Retrieved from: <https://www.efe.com/efe/comunitat->

valenciana/sociedad/una-marea-morada-de-mujeres-clama-en-valencia-
contra-la-discriminacion/50000880-3547079

El País. (2017, March 9). Día Internacional de la Mujer 2017 | Manifestación del 8 de marzo. *El País*. Retrieved from https://elpais.com/elpais/2017/03/08/actualidad/1488970669_451889.html

Europa Press (2017, March 8). El Paro Internacional de Mujeres para el 8-M también llega a España. *Elmundo.es*. Retrieved from: <https://www.elmundo.es/sociedad/2017/03/04/58bab1ec268e3e31498b4648.html>

Evans, E. & Chamberlain, P. (2015) Critical Waves: Exploring Feminist Identity, Discourse and Praxis in Western Feminism. *Social Movement Studies*, v. 14, 396-409.

Fernández Romero, D. & Núñez Puente, S. (2017). Producciones activistas online de la víctima de violencia como sujeto político. El paro internacional de mujeres #8M. In J. Sierra (Ed.), *Nuevas tecnologías audiovisuales para nuevas narrativas interactivas digitales en la era multidispositivo* (pp. 445-454). Madrid: McGraw-Hill.

Fernández Romero, D. (2019) Spain's campaigns against gender violence: the effect on abused women's identities from the victim-agent dichotomy. *Journal of Gender Studies*. DOI: [10.1080/09589236.2019.1596786](https://doi.org/10.1080/09589236.2019.1596786)

- Flesher Fominaya, C., & Gillan, K. (2017). Navigating the technology-media-movements complex. *Social Movement Studies*, 16(4), 383-402.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14742837.2017.1338943>
- Fraser, N. (2012). Reflexiones en torno a Polanyi y la actual crisis capitalista. *Papeles de relaciones ecosociales y cambio global*, 118, 13-28.
- Fuchs, C. (2013). Twitter and Democracy: A New Public Sphere. In C. Fuchs (Ed.), *Social Media, a critical introduction* (pp. 179-209). London: Sage.
- Gámez Fuentes, M.J., Gómez Nicolau, E., & Maseda García, R. (2016). Celebrities, violencia de género y derechos de las mujeres: ¿hacia una transformación del marco de reconocimiento? *Revista Latina de Comunicación Social*, 71, 833-852.
- Gámez-Fuentes, M.J., & Núñez-Puente, S. (2013). Medios, ética y violencia de género: más allá de la victimización. *Asparkia*, 24, 145-160.
- Gil de Zúñiga, H., Veenstra, A., Vraga, E., & Shah, D. (2010). Digital democracy: Reimagining pathways to political participation. *Journal of Information Technology & Politics*, 7(1), 36-51.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/19331680903316742>
- Gill, R., & Orgad, S. (2018). The Amazing Bounce-Backable Woman: Resilience and the Psychological Turn in Neoliberalism. *Sociological Research Online*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1360780418769673>
- Grabowicz, P. A., Ramasco, J. J., Moro, E., Pujol, J. M., & Eguiluz, V. M. (2012). Social Features of Online Networks: The Strength of Intermediary Ties in Online Social Media. *PLOS ONE*, 7(1), e29358. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0029358>

- Gruzd, A., Wellman, B., & Takhteyev, Y. (2011). Imagining Twitter as an Imagined Community. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 55(10), 1294–1318.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764211409378>
- Horeck, T. (2014) # AskThicke: ‘Blurred lines,’ rape culture, and the feminist hashtag takeover. *Feminist Media Studies*, 14(6): 1105–1107.
- Jenkins, H. (2008). *Convergence culture: la cultura de la convergencia de los medios de comunicación*. Barcelona: Paidós.
- Kaun, A., & Uldam, J. (2018). Digital activism: After the hype. *New Media & Society*, 20(6), 2099-2106. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444817731924>
- Khoja-Moolji, S. (2015). Becoming an “intimate publics”: Exploring the affective intensities of hashtag feminism. *Feminist Media Studies*, 15 (2), 347-350.
- Laudano, C. (2017, March 9). Entre asambleas y redes sociales se construyen el Paro Internacional de Mujeres. *Marcha.org.ar*. Retrieved from <http://www.marcha.org.ar/paro-internacional-de-mujeres-entre-asambleas-y-redes-sociales/>
- López Alvarez, C. (2017, March 3). #NosotrasParamos: el 8 de marzo las mujeres del mundo se ponen en huelga. *Lavanguardia.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.lavanguardia.com/de-moda/20170303/42465987424/huelga-mujeres-dia-de-la-mujer-8-de-marzo-nosotrasparamos.html>
- Madridiario.es* (2017, March 8). Las mujeres hacen historia: manifestación multitudinaria para reivindicar sus derechos. Retrieved from:

<https://www.madridiario.es/442168/arranco-manifestacion-dia-internacional-mujer>

Mendes, K; Ringrose, J. & Keller, J. (2018). #MeToo and the promise and pitfalls of challenging rape culture through digital feminist activism. *European Journal of Women's Studies*, 25(2) 236–246.

Moors, M. R. (2019). What is Flint? Place, storytelling, and social media narrative reclamation during the Flint water crisis. *Information, Communication & Society*, 22(6), 808-822. <https://doi.org/10/gfx7z4>

Morozov, E. (2011). *The Net Delusion: How Not to Liberate The World*. Penguin UK.

Morozov, E. (2013). *To save everything, click here: the folly of technological solutionism*.

Morstatter, F., Pfeffer, J., & Liu, H. (2014). When is it Biased? Assessing the Representativeness of Twitter's Streaming API. *arXiv:1401.7909 [physics]*. Recuperado de <http://arxiv.org/abs/1401.7909>

Mossberger, K., Tolbert, C. J., & McNeal, R. S. (2008). *Digital citizenship: The Internet, society, and participation*. MIT Press.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/19331680802290972>

Miguel, L. (2019, March 28). 'Una marabunta que escribe': retrato del estallido del #MeToo mexicano. *Eldiario.es*. Retrieved from:

https://www.eldiario.es/cultura/MeToo_0_882612542.html

Núñez Puente, S. (2011). Feminist cyberactivism: Violence against women, internet politics, and Spanish feminist praxis online. *Continuum: Journal of Media &*

Cultural Studies, 25(3), 333-346.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10304312.2011.562964>

Núñez Puente, S., Fernández Romero, D., & Vázquez Cupeiro, S. (2017). Online feminist practice, participatory activism and public policies against gender-based violence in Spain. *Feminist Theory*, 18 (3), 299-321

Núñez Puente, S., Fernández Romero, D., & Rubira García, R. (2015). Online activism and subject construction of the victim of gender-based violence on Spanish YouTube channels: Multimodal analysis and performativity. *European Journal of Women's Studies*, 22 (3), 319-333.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1350506814567002>

Oliver, K. (2001). *Witnessing: Beyond Recognition*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.

Olson CC (2016) #BringBackOurGirls: Digital communities supporting real-world change and influencing mainstream media agendas. *Feminist Media Studies* 16(5): 772-787.

Oz, M. (2016). Mainstream media's coverage of the Gezi protests and protesters' perception of mainstream media. *Global Media and Communication*, 12(2), 177-192. <https://doi.org/10/gfx7z8>

Parodemujeres.com

Park, J. H., & Suh, B. (2013). The Impact of Influential's Betweenness Centrality on the WOM Effect under the Online Social Networking Service Environment.

PACIS 2013 Proceedings. Retrieved from

<https://aisel.aisnet.org/pacis2013/60>

Peña-López, I., Congosto, M., & Aragón, P. (2014). Spanish Indignados and the evolution of the 15M movement on Twitter: towards networked para-institutions. *Journal of Spanish Cultural Studies*, 15(1-2), 189-216. <https://doi.org/10/55s>

Rajasingh, I., Rajan, B., & D, F. I. (2009). Betweenness-Centrality of Grid Networks. In

2009 International Conference on Computer Technology and Development

(Vol. 1, pp. 407–410). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCTD.2009.230>

Recuero, R., Zago, G., Bastos, M. T., & Araújo, R. (2015). Hashtags Functions in the Protests Across Brazil. *SAGE Open*, 5(2), 2158244015586000. <https://doi.org/10/gfx7sk>

Sahuquillo, M. R., & Álvarez, P. (2017, March 9). Movilización global contra la

desigualdad en el Día internacional de la mujer. *El País*. Retrieved from

https://elpais.com/internacional/2017/03/08/actualidad/1489004478_13

8303.html

Srnicek, N. (2016). *Platform Capitalism*. London: Polity Press.

Smith-Prei, C. & Stehle, M. (2016). *Awkward Politics: Technologies of Popfeminist*

Activism. Montreal: McGill-Queen's University Press.

Tanenbaun, L. (2015). *I am not a Slut: Slut-Shaming in the Age of Internet*. New York:

Harper Perennial.

The New York Times (2017, March 8). International Women's Day: Calls to Action,

Protests and Words of Praise. Retrieved from

[https://www.nytimes.com/2017/03/08/world/international-womens-](https://www.nytimes.com/2017/03/08/world/international-womens-day.html)

day.html

Tremayne, M. (2014). Anatomy of Protest in the Digital Era: A Network Analysis of Twitter and Occupy Wall Street. *Social Movement Studies*, 13(1), 110–126.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/14742837.2013.830969>

Vatikiotis, P., & Yörük, Z. F. (2016). Gezi Movement and the Networked Public Sphere: A Comparative Analysis in Global Context. *Social Media + Society*, 2(3), 2056305116662184. <https://doi.org/10/gfx7z7>

Weimann, G. (1982). On the Importance of Marginality: One More Step into the Two-Step Flow of Communication. *American Sociological Review*, 47(6), 764-773.

Zuil, M. (2017, March 3). Día de la Mujer: “Hacemos huelga para mostrar que, sin nosotras, se para el mundo”. *Elconfidencial.com*. Retrieved from: https://www.elconfidencial.com/espana/2017-03-08/dia-de-la-mujer-huelga-manifestacion_1344178/

Table 1: Synthetic Operationalization of the Concept of Ethical Testimony

Analytic dimensions	Objects of study in Social Media	Techniques/Indicators
TESTIFIER-WITNESS RELATION (PRODUCTION-PRODUCT PROCESS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of tweeters - Popular tweeters (influencers) - Relation between influencers and witnesses/victims 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accounts with the most followers, tweets, retweets, or mentions - Accounts with the highest profile, PageRank and interaction (metrics of social networks to measure influence and popularity)
CONTENT OF THE TESTIMONY	- Explicit content and absences	- Analysis of the content and lexicographical frequency of certain

	- Lexical categorization of the phenomenon in the testimony	terms (“violence,” “victim,” “institution,” etc.), noting both the presence and the absence of these terms in tweets - Analysis of pairs or groups of words: how they relate to each other and categorize those key terms - Latent semantic analysis
CONSTRUCTION OF VULNERABILITY/RESISTANCE	- Generation of grouping, agency, and intersubjectivity.	- Analysis of Social Networks: Distribution of the network, generation of conversational communities (intersubjectivity with agency) - Metrics of adhesion and going viral, capability of going beyond linear relationships and generating debate. Impact in communities which exceed the boundary of the primary connections.
CONNECTIONS WITH GENERAL FRAMEWORK	- Connection of messages to other adjacent themes. - Contextualization of gender-based violence in situations of inequality.	- Analysis of other frames and identification of wide prognostic and diagnostic frameworks. - Mapping of strong and weak connections (mentions, followers, crossed comments, tagged users, etc.).

N#	User	Characterization	Tweet	Mentions	Replies to
1	agarzon	Political person/organization	1	886	1
2	_manifiesta_	Influencer-Activist	1	413	0
3	queviv	Unknown	1	413	0
4	alejostivel	Famous person (influencers)	1	398	1
5	dosbrosuy	Famous person (influencers)	2	352	2
6	pablo_iglesias_	Political person/organization	1	190	1
7	tiempoarg	Mass media	9	179	0
8	santiagodelmoro	Famous person (influencers)	1	153	0
9	sdalmaoficial	Famous person (influencers)	1	106	5

10	la_campora	Political person/organization	3	98	0
11	el_pais	Mass media	2	94	1
12	bunnyandcurves	Unknown	4	91	0
13	redry13	Influencer-Activist	1	88	0
14	laurayjavisco	Influencer-Activist	1	85	1
15	facundo_arana	Famous person (influencers)	1	78	8
16	sanchezcastejon	Political person/organization	1	80	5
17	telefenoticias	Mass media	1	80	1
18	foeint	Influencer-Activist	2	75	0
19	sidecarsrock	Famous person (influencers)	1	70	0
20	patgarret4	Influencer-Activist	2	66	0
21	jumasa85	Political person/organization	1	64	0
22	cfkargentina	Political person/organization	1	58	6
23	nkreplak	Influencer-Activist	2	62	0
24	jodidoangel	Unknown	1	60	0
25	larroqueandres	Influencer-Activist	3	55	0

Pos.	Word	Count
	Total Words	225.856
1	Niunamenos (Not one less [woman])	17.173
2	Rt	11.180
3	8m	4.069
4	Diainternacionaldelamujer (International Women's Day)	3.639
5	Mujeres (Women)	3.448
6	Mujer (Woman)	2.585
7	Nosotrasparamos (We [women] strike)	1.959

8	Vivasnosqueremos (We want us [women] alive)	1.864
9	Lucha (Struggle)	1.549
10	Todas (All women)	1.398
11	Contra (Against)	1.372
12	Internacional (International)	1.323
13	Patriarcado (Patriarchy)	947
14	Paro (Strike)	946

Word Pairs	Count
8m,niunamenos (8M, not one less [woman])	73
nosotrasparamos,niunamenos (we [women] strike, not one less [woman]	70
un,pacto (a, pact [bilateral pact])	63
las,mujeres (the, women)	60
la,violencia (the, violence)	56
contra,la (against, the)	56
8m,nosotrasparamos (8M, we women strike)	54
niunamenos,vivasnosqueremos (not one less [woman], alive we want us [women])	53

niunamenos,todasasol (not one less [woman], all women to [La Puerta del] Sol	47
por,un (for, a)	46

Hashtag	Count
Niunamenos (Not one less [woman])	943
8m	321
Nosotrasparamos (We women strike)	108
Vivasnosqueremos (Alive we want us women)	92
Todasasol (All women to [la Puerta del] Sol)	60
Mujeresdelmundo (Women of the world)	49
Diainternacionaldelamujer (International Women's Day)	44
Mujeresenhuelga (Women on strike)	43
Wakeup	28
8marzo (March 8th)	27

Hashtag (date of extraction)	Tweets (N)	Mentions (Retweets)	Replies to	Total
#8M (March 7th)	1144 (18,3%)	5067 (81%)	40 (0,6%)	6251
#NiUnaMenos (March 8 th)	5192 (25,3%)	15045 (73,5%)	242 (1,1%)	20479

#	Twitter ID	Name	betweennesscentrality	Characterization
2	juanmatanza	JuanMa Torres	0.8	Political person/organization
3	bouty35	Boutaina_Elhadri	0.75	Influencer-Activist
5	mdaralar	Mikel De Aralar	0.7	Influencer-Activist
10	mujeresenhuelga	ParoINTdeMujeres	0.000009	Influencer-Activist

1	1	niunamenos_	NiUnaMenos	0.000008	Influencer-Activist
1	2	marceladurrieu	Marcela Durrieu	0.000007	Political person/organization
1	3	alejostivel	alejo stivel	0.000006	Famous person (influencers)
1	4	mujeresfrmoron	Mujeres FR Morón	0.000006	Influencer-Activist
1	5	mprenovacion	MujeresRenovación	0.000006	Influencer-Activist
1	6	moronolvidado	Moron Olvidado	0.000005	Influencer-Activist
1	7	_manifiesta_	MANIFIESTA	0.000004	Influencer-Activist
1	8	ugt_comunica	UGT	0.000004	Political person/organization
1	9	ugtelemadrid	Ugt Telemadrid	0.000002	Political person/organization
2	0	comoleerenbici	Como leer en bici	0.000002	Influencer-Activist
2	1	fademur	FADEMUR	0.000002	Influencer-Activist
2	2	el_pais	EL PAÍS	0.000001	Mass media
2	3	planetaeskoria_	Planeta Eskoria	0.000001	Influencer-Activist
2	4	yo_soy_asin	★Antídoto★	0.000001	Influencer-Activist
2	5	lm_lombardo	LmLombardo	0.000001	Political person/organization
2	6	cocotelemadrid	CCOOTElemadrid #925R	0.000001	Political person/organization
2	7	jumasa85	Juan Manuel	0.000001	Political person/organization
2	8	cpt_democracia	Capitán Democracia	0.000001	Influencer-Activist
2	9	soniapillado70	Sonia	0.000001	Political person/organization
3	0	maitelucerga	Maite Lucerga	0.000001	Political person/organization

Table 8: Synthesis of the principal analytic dimensions

Table 8: Synthesis of the principal analytic dimensions			
Type of campaigns	Twitter content-> Discursive frames CONTENT OF TESTIMONY LINKS TO GENERAL FRAMEWORK	Conversation and types of interventions (tweets/ retweets) CONSTRUCTION OF VILNERABILITY	Network Analysis TESTIFIER-WITNESS RELATIONSHIP

		AND RESISTANCE	
GENERAL (8# y #NiUnaMenos)	<p>Few references to the “victim” general and delocalized slogans (woman, struggle, violence, patriarchy, strike, international, world, etc.)</p> <p>Few terms that are very general, frequent and of consensus. Only general references to the idea of “violence” in a broad sense.</p> <p>Presence of accounts or organizations not related to the movement (Alberto Garzón and other politicians, Unions, etc.).</p>	<p>Hardly any debate.</p> <p>The majority are messages or tweets (nearly 20%) and the rest are almost all direct re-posts or retweets (nearly 80%). Replies do not total 1%.</p> <p>Campaigns with high level of agreement but no deliberation. Widely accepted campaigns that do not stimulate discussion.</p> <p>Retweets of institutional or official accounts.</p>	<p>No gigantic component (nobody centralizes the conversation).</p> <p>Fragmentation in small, dispersed microcommunities that do not capitalize on the conversation but do debate within their contexts.</p> <p>The influence of certain politicians, musical groups, etc. stands out.</p> <p>Dispersion and certain accounts outside the movement bring together more visible small communities.</p>

End Notes

ⁱ Another important precedent was the October 19th, 2016 strike and protest organized around the hashtag #*VivasNosQueremos* (We Want Us Alive) in Argentina to protest the murder of seven women in one week and the repression suffered during the *XXXI Encuentro Nacional de Mujeres* (31st National Meeting of Women).

ⁱⁱ This marked a historical milestone for global women's solidarity: "We are the Women's Strike. Not organizations. Not political parties. We, the women," the website <http://parodemujeres.com/> proclaimed.

ⁱⁱⁱ The dataset is public as they are tweets gathered through the Twitter API. As this information includes emails and twitter user accounts is not possible to publish online due to GDPR. But all datasets and interactive network maps are available by personal email to sergiodantonio@ucm.es.